

SPREADING DYNAMICS OF PP, PVDF, AND MAPP ON GLASS SUBSTRATES

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ABSTRACT

Wetting dynamics drive numerous processes involving liquids in contact with solid substrates with a wide range of geometries. However, almost no attention has been paid to the wetting behavior of molten drops of thermoplastic polymers, despite its importance, for example, in the processing of fiber-reinforced polymer composites. Indeed, the ability of classical theories of dynamic wetting, i.e. the hydrodynamic and the molecular-kinetic theories, to model these complex liquids is unknown. We have therefore investigated the spreading dynamics on glass, over temperatures between 200 and 260°C, of three thermoplastics: polypropylene, maleic anhydride-grafted polypropylene, and poly(vinylidene fluoride). Our results provide evidence of the suitability of the classical models to model dynamic wetting of molten polymers. Beneficially, the results suggest that the molecular-kinetic theory might be used as a new tool to characterize reactive wetting of molten polymers and provide access to Kuhn segment length.

1 INTRODUCTION

Wetting dynamics drive numerous technological processes involving liquids in contact with solid substrates with a wide range of geometries. The spreading dynamics of organic liquids and liquid metals at, respectively, room temperature and above 1000 °C have been studied extensively, both experimentally and numerically [1-5]. However, much less attention has been paid to the wetting behavior of molten drops of thermoplastic polymers, despite its importance in the processing of fiber-reinforced polymer composites [6]. There is even no knowledge about the relevancy of the classical dynamic wetting theories, i.e. the hydrodynamic approach (HD) [7] and the molecular-kinetic theory (MKT) [8], to model the behavior of these complex liquids. Actually, the slip length at the microscale and the contact line friction at the molecular scale, obtained from the HD approach and MKT respectively, can provide a comprehensive basis for understanding and elucidating the flow behaviors of polymer melts during processing. This is important for controlling the structural evolution and suppressing unstable surface defects (such as sharkskin commonly observed in polymer extrudates) of polymer products [9].

This work therefore investigates the spreading dynamics of three thermoplastics, polypropylene (PP), polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF), and maleic anhydride-grafted polypropylene (MAPP) on glass slides, at temperatures ranging between 200°C and 260°C. These polymers were chosen based on the fact that they have different physico-chemical interactions with this substrate, and are commonly used to process glass fiber-reinforced polymers. The PP/glass substrate interaction should be dominated by van der Waals interaction. In the case of PVDF, additionally to the van der Waals forces, many hydrogen bonds can be created between PVDF and the OH groups on the substrate, owing to the electronegativity of the fluorine groups [10]. In addition to physical interactions, MAPP has the capability to form chemical bonds with glass via the reaction between maleic anhydride (MA) groups and OH groups presented on the glass surface [11]. The present study checks the reliability of the classical HD approach and MKT to model the spreading dynamics of highly viscous molten polymer liquids, sheds light on the physico-chemical properties of the liquid/solid interface with the overall objective to clarify our understanding of the wetting dynamics of molten thermoplastics, and will finally identify ways to better engineer the glass/polymer interface.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

2.1 Materials

The materials used in this work are glass slide, PP, PVDF and MAPP polymers. The glass slides were obtained from Marienfeld, Germany. PP is a commercial isotactic PP (515A) with a number average molecular weight of 43×10^3 g/mol (Sabic, Germany). PVDF is also a commercial grade (Solef 1008) with a number average molecular weight of 114×10^3 g/mol, and was provided by Solvay, Belgium. MAPP is MA modified Polypropylene (Bynel 50E725) and was obtained from DuPont, Belgium. The melt flow rates for PP, PVDF and MAPP are respectively 24 g/10min, 8 g/10 min and 3 g/10min at 230 °C and 2.16 kg. All glass substrates were cleaned by Piranha solution. After this cleaning procedure, the glass surface becomes highly hydrophilic due to the exposed hydroxyl groups. These hydroxyl groups are supposed to react with anhydride groups and provide carboxylic acid groups and ester carbonyl groups across the interface. A possible chemical reaction mechanism is shown in Figure 1 [12].

Figure 1: Schematic illustration of a chemical reaction mechanism between a glass substrate and a MA group of a MAPP chain.

2.2 Rheological Measurements.

The rheological measurements were performed using an Advanced Rheological Extension System (ARES, TA Instruments, USA). A parallel-plate fixture with a diameter of 25 mm and fixed space of 1.5 mm was used to perform small amplitude oscillatory shear (SAOS) tests at angular frequencies from 0.01 to 10 rad/s with experimental temperatures in the range 200~260°C. The strain amplitude was maintained at 1% and verified to be within the linear viscoelastic response regime of all samples.

2.3 Surface Tension Measurements

A thermalized syringe and chamber (Ramé-Hart instrument co., USA) were employed to melt solid polymers to form pendant drops at a controlled temperature. Figure 2 illustrates the whole experimental process including pendant drop and spreading dynamics measurements. First, a stable pendant drop was formed (Figure 2a), from which the liquid/vapor interfacial tension (γ) could be calculated by the pendant drop method (based on images obtained from a Motic camera, Motic Images version Plus 2.0, Motic co., Germany). Then, the drop elongated by slightly screwing the piston of the syringe, until it contacted the substrate (Figure 2b). A sessile drop finally formed and spread spontaneously (Figure 2c).

Figure 2: Schematic illustration of the testing procedure. (a) pendant drop for surface tension measurements, (b) and (c) spreading dynamics.

2.4 Spreading Dynamics Measurements.

The spreading dynamics were monitored when drops touched the glass substrate (Figure 2b) in the thermalized chamber. The time when the drops contacted the glass substrate was set as the initial moment of the spreading dynamics. The entire spreading process was videotaped and then analyzed using a homemade software [13] to extract the relaxation of the contact angles and the dynamic of the drop base radius, both key parameters to characterize the dynamics. Argon gas was continuously flowed in the thermalized chamber to prevent degradation of the polymer drops during the entire experiment. The spreading experiments with each polymer drops were repeated at least three times to check repeatability.

2.5 Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

After the spreading experiments, the vicinity of the contact line was observed in a FEI XL30 FEG scanning electron microscope with a voltage of 5 kV. Prior to SEM observation, the surfaces were sputtered with platinum (Pt) in a Q150T S sputter coater (Quorum Technologies Ltd., U.K.).

3 THEORETICAL CONSIDERATIONS

Brochard-Wyart and De Gennes [14] suggested that three channels of dissipation, i.e., viscous dissipation, dissipation in the close vicinity of the solid near the contact line and dissipation in the precursor film associated with the complete wetting case, can compensate the out-of-balance interfacial tension forces. In partial wetting, the viscous dissipation described by the HD approach and the dissipation near the contact line described by the MKT are the dominant channels.

3.1 HD Approach

The HD approach [7] predicts the evolution of the dynamic contact angle θ_d as a function of the contact-line velocity V ,

$$V = \frac{\gamma}{9\eta} \left[\theta_d^3 - (\theta^0)^3 \right] \left[\ln \left(\frac{L}{L_s} \right) \right]^{-1} \quad (1)$$

where η , θ^0 , L_s and L are respectively, the liquid viscosity (Pa.s), the static contact angle ($^\circ$), the slip length (m) and a characteristic length scale of the droplet (m).

3.2 Molecular-kinetic Theory

The MKT proposed by Blake and Haynes [8] describes the contact line motion within the three-phase zone in terms of molecular displacements, i.e., jump length λ (m) and jump frequency κ^0 (Hz) between adsorption sites of the solid surface. The relationship between θ_d and the contact line velocity V is given by

$$V = 2\kappa^0 \lambda \sinh\left(\frac{\gamma(\cos \theta^0 - \cos \theta_d)}{2nk_B T}\right) \quad (2)$$

where T is the absolute temperature, k_B is the Boltzmann constant, and n is the number of adsorption sites per unit area of the substrate, usually set to λ^{-2} . When the argument of the sinh function is small, Eq. 2 can be simplified to

$$V = \frac{\gamma}{\zeta} (\cos \theta^0 - \cos \theta_d) \quad (3)$$

with ζ (Pa.s) the contact line friction per unit length of the contact line given by $\zeta = k_B T / (\kappa^0 \lambda^3)$. ζ provides an index of the energy dissipation stemming from the movement of the three-phase contact line across the surface of the solid.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Effect of Temperature on Surface Tensions and Viscosities.

Figure 3a shows the surface tension values as a function of temperature for PP, PVDF and MAPP. As expected, the surface tension decreases with temperature for all the polymers.²⁷ The surface tensions of PP are close to the results obtained by Kwok et al. [15] and Funke et al. [16], validating the current measurements. PVDF has the highest surface tension due its high polarity. Interestingly, MAPP shows a lower surface tension than PP even though the MA groups are polar. The surface depletion of MA groups [17] and lower density [18] may be responsible for the low surface tension of MAPP. Figure 3b shows the zero-shear viscosity versus temperature for the three polymers. The zero-shear viscosity is obtained from the angular frequency dependence of the complex viscosity. An increasing temperature accelerates the relaxation process of the polymer chains, resulting in a decrease in the viscosity with temperature.

Figure 3: Temperature dependence of surface tension (a) and zero-shear viscosity (b) for PP, PVDF and MAPP. Surface tensions for PP obtained by Kwok et al.[15] and Funke et al.[16] are also shown. The viscosity in (b) is estimated to contain 5% error in the following analysis, even though there is a weak flow velocity gradient.

4.2 Spreading Dynamics.

Figure 4 displays the contact angle relaxations for PP, PVDF and MAPP drops at 240 °C. It should be noted that the drops have different volumes as they detach from the filament at different time. They vary from 20 to 40 mm³. Biance et al. [19] have shown that when a liquid drop is deposited on a solid surface, the initial evolutions of the dynamic contact angles and drop radii are dominated by inertia. The effect of inertia can be distinguished by a change of slope [13] in the evolution of the contact angle relaxation, and it indicates that inertia affects the spreading dynamics of the polymer drops until the contact angles reach around 140°. The HD and MKT models do not model inertial spreading in the present work; thus, the spreading dynamics are analyzed below 140° in the following discussion.

Figure 4: Contact angle relaxation versus time for PP, PVDF and MAPP drops at 240°C in logarithmic scale, and the arrows indicate the end of the inertial regime [13].

4.3 Spreading Dynamics: HD Approach.

Figure 5a shows a typical relationship between the dynamic contact angle and contact line velocity for the three polymer drops at 240°C. The contact angle relaxations are smooth indicating that the rupture of the filament did not significantly influence the displacement of the contact-line. Figure 5a show an excellent fitting agreement between the experimental data and the model over several decades of velocities, indicating the HD approach is relevant here. The distributions for $\ln(L/L_s)$ are narrow and their temperature dependences are presented in Figure 5b. No clear trend can be identified except that the three polymers show different characteristic slip lengths with values between 236.2 and 386.2 μm , 10.6 and 20.7 μm , 39.4 and 191.0 μm for respectively PP, PVDF and MAPP (L was fixed to 1 mm). It is indeed expected that different chemical structures of the polymer chains at the liquid/solid interface generate distinct physico-chemical interactions leading thus to disparity in slip lengths. During the spreading of PP drops, slip can occur relatively easily when the drag force exerted on the adsorbed PP segments due to entanglements is larger than the weak adsorption force on the glass surface. This slip is governed by Van der Waals forces and the friction between the polymer segments and the bare surface. For PVDF, the electronegativity of the fluorine groups triggers the formation of numerous hydrogen bonds between the PVDF chains and OH groups on the glass [10]. The glass surface behaves like a fluffy carpet, and thus dampens the slip of PVDF chains by entanglements with the chains adsorbed via hydrogen bonds. In the case of MAPP drop, the slip is more complicated because the physical interactions are influenced by the chemical bonds formed between MA groups and OH groups. The MAPP slip length consists of both the disentanglement of chemically-end-tethered chains from the bulk chains and the direct desorption of interfacial PP chains without grafted MA groups from the glass surface. The latter one may significantly contribute to the total slip since it results from weak physical interaction.

Figure 5: (a) Dynamic contact angle versus contact line velocity fitted by the HD approach for the three polymer drops at 240 °C. Black symbols show the experimental results and the full lines show the best HD fits obtained using the G-Dyna software [20]. (b) Temperature dependence of $\ln(L/L_s)$ for the three polymers.

4.4 Spreading Dynamics: MKT.

It is generally accepted that the viscous dissipation is the main channel of dissipation for highly viscous systems [21]. It is unexpected that the MKT can work well for these molten polymers. Surprisingly, the fitting procedures lead to excellent agreements between the model and the experimental data (Figure 6a), suggesting that they can be analyzed in the context of this approach. The distributions for jump frequency κ^0 and jump length λ are narrow for all polymers. Figure 6b depicts the temperature dependence of λ for the three polymer drops. The values of λ show a slight increasing trend, from 1.1 to 1.4 nm for PP and PVDF, with temperature. These values can be compared with the Kuhn segment length of their freely-jointed chains [22-24]. Taking PP as an example, the reported Kuhn segment length (1.1~1.2 nm) [22, 23] is in good agreement with λ values (1.1~1.4 nm), suggesting that the wetting process is mediated by the molecular displacements of the polymer chain segments. It should be mentioned that it could be difficult to predict the likely Kuhn segment length for MAPP due to the existence of chemically-end-tethered chains. Nevertheless, it is encouraging that the λ values presented here are close to the Kuhn segment length of the polymer chains involved.

Figure 6: Dynamic contact angle versus contact line velocity fitted by MKT for the three polymer drops at 240 °C. (a) Black symbols show the experimental results and the full line show the best MKT fits. (b) The temperature dependence of jump length λ obtained in best MKT fits for the polymer drops.

Figure 7a compares the relationship between contact line friction ζ and viscosity η for the three different polymers. ζ increases with η linearly for PP and PVDF drops. This linear relationship was also found in previous experimental work [13]. The slopes of the straight lines are equal to 2.2 and

13.6 for PP and PVDF, respectively. It is intriguing to find that it indicates a non-linear relationship for the MAPP drop. This might originate from the release of free energy during the interfacial reaction [25] and the change of ν_L for MAPP because the unit of flow is likely to vary after the esterification reaction. Based on the different relationships between ζ and η for polymers with physical and chemical interactions with substrates, the MKT may be used as a new tool to detect reactive wetting. The absence of a linear relationship between contact line friction and viscosity would indicate the presence of additional chemical interactions. Figure 7b-d shows images of the polymer drops after cooling down to room temperature. An obvious interfacial failure could be observed for the PP/glass interface (Figure 7b), indicating a weak interfacial adhesion. This weak interfacial adhesion could even not resist the forces originating from vacuum-pumping when preparing samples for SEM analysis. PVDF shows a stronger adhesion proven by the availability of SEM images and the fact that its interfacial failure can be only observed in a SEM image and not with the optical microscope. MAPP in Figure 7c shows the strong interfacial adhesion due to the chemical adhesion. Contact line frictions (Figure 7a), interfacial morphologies (Figure 7b, c) for PVDF imply that the glass/PVDF interfacial strength is superior to the one of glass/PP system, as already confirmed by Fuentes et al. [26] for glass fiber/polymer composites.

Figure 7: (a) Contact line friction ζ versus viscosity η . Images of polymer drops after cooling down to the room temperature for PP (b), PVDF (b) and MAPP (d).

5 CONCLUSIONS

We have investigated the spreading dynamics of PP, PVDF and MAPP drops on glass over temperatures between 200 and 260°C. The HD approach and MKT showed both excellent agreement with the experimental data. Different values of slip length for the 3 polymers were obtained due to physico-chemical interactions with glass. The physical interaction dominated systems (PP and PVDF) show a linear relationship between contact line friction ζ and viscosity η , whereas the MAPP shows a non-linear relationship. Based on the different relationships, the MKT may be used as a new tool to detect reactive wetting. Besides, contact line frictions and interfacial morphologies for PVDF imply that the glass/PVDF interfacial strength is superior to the one of glass/PP system.

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